
Acceptance of Chapter Proposal and Submission of Full Chapter

1 message

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Dear Author

Thank you for submitting your chapter proposal.

We are pleased to inform you that your chapter has been accepted for inclusion in the publication. We appreciate your contribution and look forward to reviewing the complete manuscript.

Kindly share the full chapter at your earliest convenience, in accordance with the prescribed guidelines and timeline. Should you have any questions regarding formatting or submission requirements, please feel free to contact us.

We look forward to receiving your full chapter soon.

Warm regards,

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Coordinator

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